

Live Review Registration Form Text

Zoom Registration form to be set up by PREreview

PREreview and [COLLABORATOR] Live Review

Date & Time [SET ON ZOOM]

Description

PREreview and [COLLABORATOR] invite you to join an interactive live review of this preprint:

[TITLE] by [AUTHORS] - [PREPRINT SERVER]: [DOI]

Please ensure you read the preprint prior to the event.

The call will last 90 minutes and will be facilitated by the PREreview team who will guide participants through a series of questions following a collaborative noted document similar to this.

The call will be recorded but the recording will not be shared outside of the organizing team.

The review resulting from the call will be shared and published on [PREreview.org](#) under a [CC BY 4.0 license](#).

Participants will have the option to help compose and sign the final review using their real name (via their [ORCID iD](#)) or via a pseudonym provided by the PREreview account.

The [COLLABORATOR] editorial team will consider the review as an addition to their standard journal workflow protocol.

Please email us at community@prereview.org if you have any questions or concerns. Feel free to share this opportunity with colleagues.

Additional questions in registration

- How did you hear about this event?
- Would you consider being the discussion chair for this call? (The discussion chair is someone with subject matter expertise in the topic of the preprint who works with the facilitators to help guide a constructive discussion)
 - Yes
 - No
 - Maybe (please send me more details)
- Would you like to be contacted about other similar opportunities in the future?
- Questions and comments